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A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON EXTENDED RELEASE FORMULATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Oral drug delivery is the most preferred route of drug administration. Hydrophilic matrices are widely used platform for oral extended release drug delivery around the globe and most extensively studied. This is due to their broad regulatory acceptance, relative ease of formulation and manufacturing and historical commercial success in the market place. The use of extended release products offers some potential advantages in patient convenience/compliance and therapeutic outcomes. However, the range of drugs for which clinically significant advantages have been shown is limited. Prescribers and pharmacists should be aware of the costs of these products and have knowledge of their clinical use in selected patient groups. In some instances, the formulation is probably serving a marketing objective rather than a clinical objective. This article will review the importance of the extended release drug delivery system and critical formulation aspects of hydrophilic matrix technology with emphasis on the influence of polymers on their release performance.

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INTRODUCTION:

Oral administration remains the most popular route for drug delivery and tablets are the preferred dosage form. Tablets offer safe and convenient method of active pharmaceutical ingredients (API) administration with excellent physico chemical stability and accurate dosing. They are mass produced with robust quality controls and provide different branding possibilities through pigmented film coating, shapes, sizes, printing and logos [1]. Extended release (ER) formulations are designed to allow at least a twofold reduction in dosing frequency or significant increase in patient compliance or therapeutic performance when compared to a conventional immediate release dosage form [2]. Oral drug delivery system is the most popular route, which is due in part to the ease of administration and to the fact that gastrointestinal physiology offers more flexibility in dosage form design than most other routes [3]. Oral ingestion is the traditionally preferred route of drug administration, providing a convenient method of effectively achieving both local and systemic effects. In conventional oral drug delivery systems, there is very little control over release of the drug. The effective concentration at the target site can be achieved by intermittent administration of grossly excessive doses, which, in most situations, often results in constantly changing, unpredictable and often sub or supra-therapeutic plasma concentrations leading to marked side effects. An ideal oral drug delivery system should steadily deliver a measurable and reproducible amount of drug to the target site over a prolonged period [4]. Oral route generally consider an ideal drug delivery system that will possess two main properties:

- a) It should be in a single dose for prolonging action.
- b) It should be deliver the active drug directly to the target site [5].

Oral drug delivery method is the most widely utilized routes for administration among all alternatives that have been explored for systemic delivery of drug via various pharmaceutical products of different dosage forms. Popularity of the route may be ease of

administration as well as traditional belief that by oral administration the drug is due to the well absorbed into the food stuff ingested daily [6]. Extended release and delayed release are the most common type of modified release dosage forms. Extended release dosage forms allow the rate of drug-substance release to be controlled in such a manner as to allow a reduction in dosing frequency. The rate of drug-substance release is controlled by the inclusion of excipients that retard drug substance release [7].

TERMINOLOGY:

Modified Release Drug Product: The term modified release drug product is used to describe products that alter the timing and/or the rate of release of the drug substance.

Types of Modified Release Drug Products:

Extended Release Dosage Forms: A dosage form that allows at least a twofold reduction in dosage frequency as compared to that drug presented as an immediate release form.

Sustained release: It includes any drug delivery system that achieves slow release of drugs over an extended period of time not particularly at a predetermined rate.

Controlled release: It includes any drug delivery system from which the drug is delivered at a predetermined rate over a long period.

Delayed Release: A dosage form releases a discrete portion of drug at a time, than promptly after administration, although one portion may be released promptly after administration. Ex: Enteric coated dosage forms.

Targeted Release Dosage Forms: A dosage forms that releases drug at /near the intended physiological site of action. Targeted release dosage forms may have extended release characteristics.

Repeat Action Dosage Forms: It is a type of modified release drug product that is designed to release one dose or drug initially followed by a second dose of drug at a later time.

Prolonged Action Dosage Forms: It is designed to release the drug slowly and to provide a

continuous supply of drug over an extended period [8].

Advantages:

Reduction in drug plasma level fluctuations: Maintenance of a steady plasma level of the drug over a prolonged time period, ideally simulating an intravenous infusion of a drug.

Reduction in adverse side effects: Drug plasma levels are maintained and improvement in tolerability within a narrow window with no sharp peaks and with AUC of plasma concentration versus time curve comparable with total AUC from multiple dosing with immediate release dosage forms. This greatly reduces the possibility of side effects (see Figure 1), as the scale of side effects increase as we approach the MSC. Patient comfort and compliance Oral drug delivery is the most common and convenient for patients, and a reduction in dosing frequency enhances compliance.

Reduction in healthcare cost: The total cost of therapy of the controlled release product could be comparable or lower than the immediate-release product. With reduction in side effects, the overall expense in disease management also would be reduced.

Figure 1: Plasma drug concentration profiles for conventional tablet or capsule formulation (---) and a zero-order controlled-release formulation (—). MEC = Minimum Effective Concentration; MSC = Maximum Safe Concentration.

Controlled-release technology evolved with matrix technology. Several articles in the

1950s and 1960s reported simple matrix tablets or monolithic granules. In 1952, Smith Kline & French introduced the Spansule, a timed-release formulation that launched a widespread search for other applications in the design of dosage forms [9].

The goal behind the development of oral controlled-release formulations at that time was the achievement of a constant release rate of the entrapped drug. On the basis of that concept, the zero-order osmotic delivery system used in Procardia XL became one of the top 10 bestselling medicines in the past century. The size and frequency of dosing is determined by the pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic properties of the drug. The slower the rate of absorption, the less the blood concentrations fluctuate within a dosing interval. This enables higher doses to be given less frequently. For drugs with relatively short half-lives, the use of extended-release products may maintain therapeutic concentrations over prolonged periods (Figure. 1) [10].

With conventional dosage forms, high peak blood concentrations may be reached soon after administration with possible adverse effects related to the transiently high concentration. An example is hypotension in patients taking rapid-release nifedipine products. The use of an extended-release product avoids the high initial blood concentrations which cause the sudden reduction in blood pressure and other significant haemodynamic changes such as reflex tachycardia. Another example is the transient nausea at sub-toxic concentrations which results from the local irritation caused by high intestinal concentrations of some conventional-release products such as theophylline.

Improved patient compliance: Drugs with short half-lives often need to be given at frequent intervals to maintain blood concentrations within the therapeutic range. There is an inverse correlation between the frequency of dosing and patient compliance. A reduction in the number of daily doses offered by extended-release products has the potential to improve compliance. However, this advantage probably only occurs when

conventional formulations need to be given 3 or more times a day [11].

Disadvantages:

For many controlled-release products, the release rate can be altered by various factors including food and the rate of transit through the gut. There may be some differences in the release rate from one dose to another, but these have been minimised by modern formulations.

Extended-release products contain a higher drug load and thus any loss of integrity of the release characteristics of the dosage form has potential problems. While some extended-release products can be divided to provide half-doses others should only be taken whole. Modified-release products should never be crushed or chewed as the slow-release characteristics may be lost and toxicity may result. This is particularly important in patients unable to swallow whole tablets, a problem commonly affecting the elderly. The larger size of extended-release products may cause difficulties in ingestion or transit through the gut. These problems may result in some drugs, e.g. Slow-K, causing local tissue damage in patients who have a pathological or drug-induced reduction in gut motility [11].

Types of extended-release products:

Diffusion-controlled products: In these systems, there is a water-insoluble polymer which controls the flow of water and the subsequent egress of dissolved drug from the dosage form. Both diffusion and dissolution processes are involved. In 'reservoir' devices, a core of drug is coated with the polymer and, in 'matrix' systems, the drug is dispensed throughout the matrix. Cellulose derivatives are commonly used in the reservoir types, while the matrix material may be plastics, e.g. methylacrylate-methyl methacrylate, polyvinyl chloride, hydrophilic polymers such as cellulose derivatives or fatty compounds including carnauba wax. Examples of this type of formulation include Plendil ER, Agon SR, Kapanol and Slow-K.

Dissolution-controlled products:

In these products, the rate of dissolution of the drug is controlled by slowly soluble polymers or by micro encapsulation. Once the coating is dissolved, the drug becomes available for dissolution. By varying the thicknesses of the coat and its composition, the rate of drug release can be controlled. Some preparations contain a fraction of the total dose as an immediate-release component to provide a pulse dose soon after administration. The pellet dosage forms of diffusion- or dissolution-controlled products can be encapsulated or prepared as a tablet. These products should not be chewed as the coating may be damaged. One of the advantages of encapsulated pelleted products is that the onset of absorption is less sensitive to stomach emptying. The entrance of the pellets into the small intestine (where the majority of drug absorption occurs) is usually more uniform than with non-disintegrating extended-release tablet formulations. An example of this type of product is Fefol.

Erosion products:

The release of drug from these products is controlled by the erosion rate of a carrier matrix. The rate of release is determined by the rate of erosion. An example of this formulation is Sinemet CR. With this product, some patients may experience a later onset of effect after the morning dose, compared to conventional levodopa tablets, because of the delayed release of the drug.

Osmotic pump systems:

The rate of release of drug in these products is determined by the constant inflow of water across a semi permeable membrane into a reservoir which contains an osmotic agent. The drug is either mixed with the agent or is located in a reservoir. The dosage form contains a small hole from which dissolved drug is pumped at a rate determined by the rate of entrance of water due to osmotic pressure. The rate of release is constant and can be controlled within tight limits yielding relatively constant blood concentrations. The advantage of this type of product is that the constant release is unaltered by the environment of the gastrointestinal tract and relies simply on the passage of water into the dosage form. The rate of release can be modified by altering the

osmotic agent and the size of the hole. An example of this type of product is Adalat Oros.

Ion exchange resins: Some drugs can be bound to ion exchange resins and, when ingested, the release of drug is determined by the ionic environment within the gastrointestinal tract. Examples of this type of product are Duromine containing the basic drug phentermine complexed onto an anionic resin, and MS Contin suspension which uses a polystyrene sulphonate resin [12].

Mechanism of action:

Figure 2: Schematic representation of a hydrophilic matrix undergoing hydration, swelling and dissolution

After oral administration and exposure to aqueous medium, the polymer in hydrophilic matrix tablet quickly hydrates on the surface and forms a gel layer around the tablet. This phenomenon is also referred to as glassy to rubbery state transition of polymer. The outermost layer of gelled polymer reaches a dilution point where it no longer has structural integrity and the polymer finally disentangles and leaves the surface of the matrix. This phenomenon is referred to as erosion. On a molecular level, a highly coiled long chain and branched molecule when comes in contact with water, starts uncoiling due to formation of hydrogen bond with water. This initial hydration of the polymeric molecule is seen as a viscous gel layer formation, causing an increased in the volume of the matrix (this mechanism is referred to as swelling). As time progresses and more and more polymeric molecular chain gets uncoiled due to hydration, weaker the gel becomes on the outer region of the gel structure. Finally when the entire polymeric molecule is uncoiled, (fully hydrated, mechanism referred to as relaxation), it finally disentangles from the surface of the matrix

(referred to as erosion or dissolution). Figure 2 shows the overall mechanisms involved while the matrix undergoes hydration, swelling and drug release [1].

Polymers: Hydrogel polymers were much investigated in literature on basis of drug release and release mechanism from hydrophilic matrix tablets as well as pellets. HPMC polymers achieve considerable attention due to their unique properties, and they can display good compression characteristics, including when directly compressed. They are nontoxic and can accommodate high level of drug loading, and also having adequate swelling properties that allows rapid formation of an external gel layer which retards or plays a major role in controlling drug release. Furthermore, HPMC polymers are well known as pH-independent materials this advantage enables them to withstand fluctuations of pH induce by intra and inter subject variations of both gastric pH and gastrointestinal transit time. They have been used alone or in combination in formulation of matrix tablets, therefore the hydrophilic gel forming matrix tablets are extensively used for oral extended release dosage forms due to their simplicity, cost effectiveness and reduction of the risk of systemic toxicity which happens as a result of dose dumping [13] investigated the release of diclofenac sodium from a mixture of HPMC, Carbopol 940, and lactose as water soluble fillers. The results showed that the combination of hydrogels retarded the drug better than single polymer. S. Freiberg, X.X. Zhu developed once daily propranolol extended release tablets using HPMC polymer as a retarding agent [14]. The mechanism of the drug release from HPMC matrix tablet followed non-Fickian diffusion, while the in vivo absorption and in vitro dissolution showed a linear relationship. Other polymers used in hydrophilic matrix preparations include poly ethylene oxide [15].

Conclusion:

A wide range of drugs are now formulated in a variety of different oral extended release dosage forms. However, only those which result in a significant reduction in dose frequency and reduction in toxicity resulting from high

concentrations in the blood or gastrointestinal tract are likely to improve therapeutic outcomes.

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